

Fur

also known as “Darfur”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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“Darfur, or Darfor, means the land of the Fors, who were once the owners and sole inhabitants of the whole province. They have, however, been driven back into the western part of the country, the remainder of which is now inhabited by various invaders...” (Felkin, 1885:205). This entry focuses on the Fur living in the Jebel Marra area of Darfur around the time of 1880. Although Darfur was taken by the Egyptians in the 1870’s, the province of Jebel Marra was not actually subjugated until 1881 when the last sultan (Haroun) was killed. Darfur later became a province of Sudan in the 1910’s. At the time this entry focuses on, Darfur was divided into five provinces (each ruled by an official), with each province subdivided into smaller districts led by local governors. A hereditary sultan oversaw Darfur as a whole. After centuries of cultural contact with Arab peoples and Islamic beliefs, the Fur are primarily Muslim, but elements of their original beliefs remain (such as agricultural festivals, and they have laws differing from those of the Koran). The Fur religious beliefs center on Molu, the one high god. Also present are spirits of the deceased, but these supernatural beings are not involved in daily life. Religious practitioners known as puggee’s had influence over the Sultan and chiefs, and were often more powerful than chiefs. Any male could become a puggee after training in reading, writing, and the Koran, as well as Fur law. Religion does not have its own distinctive sphere in Fur life; rather, it is bound up with the functioning of society as a whole. Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society.

Date Range: 1870 CE - 1895 CE

Region: Jebel Marra, Sudan

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Sudan

Jebel Marra, West Darfur state, Sudan ca. 1880

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Felkin, R. W. (1885). Notes on the Fur tribe. Proceedings of the Royal Society of Edinburgh, 23: 205-265.
- Source 2: Beaton, A. C. (1939). Fur rain cults and ceremonies. Sudan Notes and Records, 22: 181-203.
- Source 3: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "It is a very difficult matter, if not impossible, to give any account of the original religion of the Fors. Mohammedanism has been professed by them for hundreds of years; at the same time it is tempered by their original beliefs, and a great many of its tenets are totally ignored" (Felkin, 1885:218).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, coded the Fur as not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period (as reported by ethnographer), SCCS Variable 1649 (Frequency of Internal Warfare, Resolved Rating) was coded as don't know or unclear (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), was originally coded as 4.5, which is between "external warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season", and "external warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Religion does not have its own distinctive sphere in Fur society, rather, it is bound up with the functioning of society as a whole. Consequently, religion is coterminous with the society, and there is not a system for assigning religious affiliation aside from being born into Fur society.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the recruitment of new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "The puggees have a great deal of influence over the sultan and chiefs, who consult them much, and generally follow their advice. They take precedence over the chiefs, and nobody is allowed to eat with the sultan but the priests. Chiefs are sometimes priests too" (Felkin, 1885:220).

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– I don't know

Notes: No evidence for the presence of religious infrastructure.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The head of the polity (the sultan) is distinct from the puggées (priests), although the puggées have influence over the sultan.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: "The puggées have a great deal of influence over the sultan and chiefs, who consult them much, and generally follow their advice. They take precedence over the chiefs, and nobody is allowed to eat with the sultan but the priests. Chiefs are sometimes priests too" (Felkin, 1885:220).

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: The chiefs and puggées [priests] act as judges, and enforce Fur law, which is based in religion (see Felkin, 1885:245-246).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 120000

Notes: "The whole population of Darfur may be roughly estimated at from 3 to 5 millions, about half that number being Fors; but it is impossible to obtain exact information on this point" (Felkin, 1885:205-206). "Of a total Fur population of about 160,000 souls three quarters live in the Western District and it is with them that these notes are concerned" (Beaton, 1939:188).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Fors have priests or fakirs, who go by the name of puggées" (Felkin, 1885:220).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: "There are three ranks of priests; they wear little white caps, the embroidery of which tells their status. Although each puggée is under no practical obligation to obey those of higher rank, still they do defer to their opinions, and are ready and willing to receive instruction from them. The difference in rank is caused by age and experience; those men too who have been a pilgrimage to Mecca are naturally more respected and hold a higher rank than their

fellows" (Felkin, 1885:220-221).

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: "The Fors have priests or fakirs, who go by the name of puggees. They are in no sense hereditary, and there is no ceremonial induction into their office. Any one may become a puggee if he chooses, but he must first be educated by a priest, in reading and writing, in the Koran, and in the For law; for the Fors have a written law, which differs considerably from that found in the Koran" (Felkin, 1885:220).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: In order to become a puggee (priest), an individual must be educated in the Koran (Felkin, 1885:220).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Koran is a written text.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– I don't know

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Stone huts

Notes: "There are still a few stone huts in existence, which were devoted to the worship of Molu before Mohammedanism was introduced, and the people still reverence them" (Felkin, 1885:222).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: "Some few of them go on pilgrimages to Mecca..." (Felkin, 1885:219).

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "'Kilma' is what seems to correspond to our idea of 'soul.' It is called 'the power of the liver,' for, believing that the liver is the seat of the soul, it is considered that an increase of a man's own soul may be obtained by partaking of an animal's liver...Women are not allowed to eat liver, and are believed not to possess a 'kilma.' When a man dies his kilma is supposed to go to Accra, and there he is told whether he has been good enough to go to Molu. Molu is the ancient native name for God" (Felkin, 1885:218).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "When a man dies his kilma is supposed to go to Accra, and there he is told whether he has been good enough to go to Molu. Molu is the ancient native name for God" (Felkin, 1885:218). "The dead are supposed only to stay in Accra about a day, when, if they have been good, they go to Molu, who lives in Jouel, 'the sky,' and are very happy there" (ibid. pg. 219).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead are supposed only to stay in Accra about a day, when, if they have been good, they go to Molu, who lives in Jouel, 'the sky,' and are very happy there" (Felkin, 1885:219).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Funerals take place within a few hours of death. The corpse is wrapped in a winding shroud of damoor cloth, and carried to the grave on a rude bier hastily constructed of wooden poles lashed together with rope. It is not used a second time, but is burnt. Graves are dug 6 or 8 feet deep and covered with stones, but the Arab method of burial is being rapidly introduced into the country. The graveyards are situated at some considerable distance from the villages" (Felkin, 1885:229).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: (Felkin, 1885:229)

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the practice of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850 (Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale), secondary bone/body treatment is absent (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: "No animals are offered as a sacrifice at funerals" (Felkin, 1885:230). Further, no ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice was found.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Funerals take place within a few hours of death. The corpse is wrapped in a winding shroud of damoor cloth, and carried to the grave in a rude bier hastily constructed of wooden poles lashed together with rope. It is not used a second time, but is burnt. Graves are dug 6 or 8 feet deep and covered with stones, but the Arab method of burial is being rapidly introduced into the country. The graveyards are situated at some considerable distance from the village" (Felkin, 1885:229).

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "Graves are dug 6 or 8 feet deep and covered with stones, but the Arab method of burial is being rapidly introduced into the country. The graveyards are situated at some considerable distance from the village" (Felkin, 1885:229).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family tomb-crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence that the deceased are interred beneath domestic areas.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts of departed spirits are called 'Malal'; they are said to appear to their friends most frequently during the first few nights after their decease..." (Felkin, 1885:219-220). "The one God Molu, who lives in the sky, is believed in and worshipped. He is regarded as the Creator of men, and as Supreme Ruler of the world" (Felkin, 1885:221).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The one God Molu, who lives in the sky, is believed in and worshiped. He is regarded as the Creator of men, and as the Supreme Ruler of the World" (Felkin, 1885:221).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead are supposed only to stay in Accra about a day, when, if they have been good, they go to Molu, who lives in Jouel, 'the sky,' and are very happy there" (Felkin, 1885:219).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Prosperity and adversity alike are believed to be the result of his [Molu] ordaining; and when evil happens or death occurs the people console themselves and each other by saying that they could not help it, and that Molu willed it" (Felkin, 1885:221).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts of departed spirits are called 'Malal'; they are said to appear to their friends most frequently during the first few nights after their decease..." (Felkin, 1885:219-220).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghosts of departed spirits are called 'Malal'; they are said to appear to their friends most frequently during the first few nights after their decease, and to be clad from head to foot in white damoor cloth (this material forms their shroud), and they appear much taller than when in life. They are supposed to visit houses during the night, and to alter the position of different articles of furniture" (Felkin, 1885:219-220).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Malal are described as visiting their friends during the first nights after their death. If the Malal have memory of who their friends were, the Malal presumably have memory of life. (see Felkin, 1885:219-220).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not specified if the following supernatural beings are non-human. "The Fors have another very strong belief, which has been unaffected by the Mohammedan religion, that a great spirit lives on the summit of Gebel Marah. They do not worship him, but they believe he has an innumerable army of spirit servants, zittan, who possess extraordinary powers. A limited number of magicians are supposed to stand in intimate relation to this great mountain spirit..." (Felkin, 1885: 222).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: The following passage indicates that bad behavior will result in punishment after death, implying that Molu will be aware of such behavior. However, no further details concerning supernatural monitoring are found. "They attach considerable importance to the rainbow, believing that Molu causes it to ascend from the water to the sky in order to prevent men thinking that there is no God, and to warn them that if they do not behave themselves they will be burnt up in Uddu with fire like the red of the rainbow" (Felkin, 1885:221).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for available information concerning supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Of the ethnographic examples of supernatural punishment, only Molu was described as the cause of such punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not explicitly stated in ethnographic materials that Molu is the only agent of supernatural punishment. The spirits of deceased humans are present, but are not described in great details. Insufficient ethnographic evidence to make a conclusive decision.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "They attach considerable importance to the rainbow, believing that Molu causes it to ascend from the water to the sky in order to prevent men thinking that there is no God, and to warn them that if they do not behave themselves they will be burnt up in Uddu with fire like the red of the rainbow" (Felkin, 1885:221).

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead are supposed only to stay in Accra about a day, when, if they have been good, they go to Molu, who lives in Jouel, 'the sky,' and are very happy there. If they have been wicked, they go to Uddu, the place of punishment, where they meet with all sorts of disagreeable things, and are finally burnt up" (Felkin, 1885:219).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Felkin, 1885:219

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence concerning supernatural reward to make a conclusive decision.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The words used to express right and wrong are those which denote also good and bad; namely Tulai, good, and Gettee, bad. A good man is one who is truthful and honest, brave, and kind to animals, who bears pain with fortitude, and is loyal to his neighbors and his sultan; the bad man is the reverse of all this" (Felkin, 1885:232-233).

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: kind to animals

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: "Suicide is unknown in Darfur" (Felekin, 1885:231).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required sacrifice of property/valuable items.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "The old custom of praying to Molu has become almost obsolete, and has been replaced to some extent by a few prayers from the Koran learnt from the puggees. The practice of regular prayer, however, is now limited to the educated classes, and the poor people do not pray at all" (Felkin, 1885:223).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Notes: Aside from life-cycle events, two important festivals are held. "Sowing the seed" is an agricultural event associated with the beginning of the planting season. During this event, multiple villages of a district come together, pray to Molu [high god], sing, and dance. Secondly, the Mohammedan feast of Bairam (lasting 8-10 days), begins with men meeting to say prayers, followed by the entire community gathering for feasting, singing, and dancing. It is unclear if participation in these rituals is mandatory. For more information, see Felkin, 1885"225-226).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Fur have three levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a state-level society (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Further, the society is stratified, enforces laws, and are capable of drafting men for war (see Felkin, 1885:240-246). "The Fors have had a long hereditary line of despotic sultans, the last of whom, Haroun, was killed by the Egyptian troops in 1881, after I visited Darfur. Until this time the sultans lived in great state, and the Arab tribes who had encroached upon their country had been compelled to pay them taxes in order to enjoy their protection...Darfur was divided into five large provinces, severally ruled by a high dignitary of state, and each of these provinces were subdivided into small districts under the management of shartays or local governors" (Felkin, 1885:244).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: "Any one may become a puggee if he chooses, but he must first be educated by a priest, in reading and writing, in the Koran, and in the For law; for the Fors have a written law, which differs

considerably from that found in the Koran...The pugges are the teachers of all who wish to learn but the instruction they give is very meager; only a little reading and writing are taught, and a few prayers from the Koran. The schools are held in the evening after the work of the day is over, and are conducted by firelight" (Felkin, 1885:220).

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Felkin, 1885:220

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: "Those who are going to be educated for priests live in a pugges's village, where only pugges and their pupils reside. There are sometimes 200 or 300 of the latter, and no females are permitted there" (Felkin, 1885:224).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: "With the exception of the schools for boys who are set apart for a higher education, the children do not receive much schooling" (Felkin, 1885:224).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "The roads in the northern and north-eastern parts of Darfur are simply paths which lead through the open country. In the south, paths between villages are worn by use. No roads are made" (Felkin, 1885:251).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: "The chiefs are compelled to pay certain taxes to the sultan, which they must present in person" (Felkin, 1885:245).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The taxes then paid to the Egyptian Government were in tobs [cloth] or grain, and the inhabitants were obliged to provide camels and oxen for transport, but for these they were paid at a fixed rate in tobs" (Felkin, 1885:250).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: "A class of regular soldiers exists in Darfur, and they are called dalimars. They are in the service of the chiefs, and any strong young man may enlist in their ranks, but they receive no regular pay. They are liable to be called on for service at any time, and they then receive proper rations of food, and at the close of a war they get presents of damoor cloth and grain...The dalimars are employed very much as a police force in times of peace" (Felkin, 1885:240-241).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: "The chiefs and puggees are the judges" (Felkin, 1885:245).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Fors have a written law, which differs considerably from that found in the Koran" (Felkin, 1885:220).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: "A class of regular soldiers exists in Darfur, and they are called dalimars. They are in the service of the chiefs, and any strong young man may enlist in their ranks, but they receive no regular pay. They are liable to be called on for service at any time, and they then receive proper rations of food, and at the close of a war they get presents of damoor cloth and grain" (Felkin, 1885:240).

Written Language

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The only writing in Darfur is in the Arabic character. Few people use it, but it must have been introduced centuries ago, as all the books of For law, and those giving instruction in the preparation of

drugs and charms, are written in the For language in Arabic characters" (Felkin, 1885:264).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Fur rely primarily on intensive agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry serves as a secondary source of subsistence, and fishing supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Fur rely primarily on intensive agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry serves as a secondary source of subsistence, and fishing supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.